

APPENDIX Y: Post-Workshop Survey Questionnaire

Memoriscapes in Recto-spection: Visualizing Avenida, Recto, and Carriedo, Manila as Virtual Memoriscapes through immersive mobile technologies and digital heritage interpretation

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MEMORISCAPES IN RECTO-SPECTION
Envisioning Avenida, Recto, and Carriedo, Manila as Virtual Memoriscapes Through Immersive Mobile Technologies and Digital Heritage Interpretation

Post-Workshop Questionnaire

Good day!

I am **Leijh Hanne Y. Alianza**, a senior undergraduate student from the University of the Philippines Diliman - College of Architecture under the Landscape Architecture program. I am currently conducting a study entitled **"Memoriscapes in Recto-spection: Envisioning Avenida, Recto, and Carriedo, Manila as Virtual Memoriscapes Through Immersive Mobile Technologies and Digital Heritage Interpretation"**. This study aims to create a Virtual Memoriscapes toolkit that seeks to reimagine the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip as a Virtual Memoriscapes through the co-design workshop sessions with the community and stakeholders of the study site as a demonstration of the toolkit. The study also aims to highlight the needs of the community and to showcase the significance of the study site as a former commercial and entertainment district through mobile augmented reality.

Part of my study consists of conducting a Landscape Perception and Preference Survey to determine the public's current perception of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip, and their preferences on its surrounding open spaces and streetscapes. The results of this survey would be used as the basis for further investigations conducted in this study.

A portion of my methodology was based on Sundberg (2016), Hedblom et al (2019), Nadal, (2021), and Trias, (2022). These studies were used as reference for the present survey.

With this, I respectfully request your help in answering this short survey. In answering this survey, I will ensure that your answers are used only for this study, and that your personal data will be kept confidential and secure.

If you have any further questions, you may contact me via email at lyalianza@up.edu.ph.

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* Indicates required question

If you have any further questions, you may contact me via email at lyalianza@up.edu.ph.

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* Indicates required question

Email *

Record lyalianza@up.edu.ph as the email to be included with my response

DATA PRIVACY AND INFORMED CONSENT *

The data obtained from this survey will be treated as highly confidential and will be used exclusively for academic purposes. It will be kept anonymous in compliance with Republic Act (R.A.) No. 10173, also known as the "Data Privacy Act of 2012". By consenting to participate in this survey, the student researcher is authorized to access and process your personal information. For more information on the Data Privacy Act of 2012, please visit the following link: <https://www.privacy.gov.ph/data-privacy-act/>.

If you willingly and voluntarily agree to participate in this survey and have your personal data and information gathered and analyzed, please respond with YES. By answering YES in this consent form, you are allowing the researcher to use your responses for the thesis entitled **"Memoriscapes in Recto-spection: Envisioning Avenida, Recto, and Carriedo, Manila as Virtual Memoriscapes Through Immersive Mobile Technologies and Digital Heritage Interpretation"**.

YES, I understand the aforementioned statement and hereby grant my consent to be part of this online survey as a qualified participant in accordance with the criteria of this study.

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DEMOGRAPHIC ASSESSMENT	PERCEIVED USEFULNESS
<p>Email *</p> <p>Your answer _____</p>	<p>Using the Virtual Memoriscapes Toolkit and the CALSADA AR would enable me * to accomplish participatory planning sessions more quickly compared to traditional plenary/design sessions.</p> <p>1 2 3 4 5</p> <p>Strongly Disagree (Lubos na Di-Sumasangayon) ☐ ☐ ☐ ☐ ☐ Strongly Agree (Lubos na Sumasangayon)</p>
<p>Name (Pangalan) *</p> <p>Your answer _____</p>	<p>Using the Virtual Memoriscapes Toolkit and the CALSADA AR would improve my * visualization of 2D images or drawings compared to traditional plenary/design sessions.</p> <p>1 2 3 4 5</p> <p>Strongly Disagree (Lubos na Di-Sumasangayon) ☐ ☐ ☐ ☐ ☐ Strongly Agree (Lubos na Sumasangayon)</p>
<p>Sex Assigned at Birth (Kasarian) *</p> <p>☐ Lalaki</p> <p>☐ Babae</p> <p>☐ Prefer not to disclose</p>	<p>Using the Virtual Memoriscapes Toolkit and the CALSADA AR would improve my * productivity and attentiveness in a co-design workshop session.</p> <p>1 2 3 4 5</p> <p>Strongly Disagree (Lubos na Di-Sumasangayon) ☐ ☐ ☐ ☐ ☐ Strongly Agree (Lubos na Sumasangayon)</p>
<p>Age (Edad) *</p> <p>Your answer _____</p>	<p>Using the Virtual Memoriscapes Toolkit and the CALSADA AR would enhance * my participation in a co-design workshop session.</p> <p>1 2 3 4 5</p> <p>Strongly Disagree (Lubos na Di-Sumasangayon) ☐ ☐ ☐ ☐ ☐ Strongly Agree (Lubos na Sumasangayon)</p>
<p>Occupation/Designation (Trabaho/Katungkulan) *</p> <p>Your answer _____</p>	
<p>Place of Residence (Tirahan) *</p> <p>Your answer _____</p>	
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Using the Virtual Memoriscapes Toolkit and the CALSADA AR would make it easier to do participatory planning sessions compared to traditional plenary/design sessions. *

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree (Lubos na Di-Sumasangayon) Strongly Agree (Lubos na Sumasangayon)

I would find the Virtual Memoriscapes Toolkit and the CALSADA AR useful and relevant to my job. *

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree (Lubos na Di-Sumasangayon) Strongly Agree (Lubos na Sumasangayon)

I would find the Virtual Memoriscapes Toolkit and the CALSADA AR filled with valuable information about streetscapes and the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip's history. *

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree (Lubos na Di-Sumasangayon) Strongly Agree (Lubos na Sumasangayon)

I would find the Virtual Memoriscapes Toolkit and the CALSADA AR useful in conducting participatory planning sessions with people who have non-design backgrounds. *

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree (Lubos na Di-Sumasangayon) Strongly Agree (Lubos na Sumasangayon)

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PERCEIVED EASE OF USE

Learning how to use the Virtual Memoriscapes Toolkit and the CALSADA AR was easy for me. *

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree (Lubos na Di-Sumasangayon) Strongly Agree (Lubos na Sumasangayon)

I would find it easy to get the Virtual Memoriscapes Toolkit and the CALSADA AR to do what I want it to do. *

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree (Lubos na Di-Sumasangayon) Strongly Agree (Lubos na Sumasangayon)

My interaction with the Virtual Memoriscapes Toolkit and the CALSADA AR would be clear and understandable. *

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree (Lubos na Di-Sumasangayon) Strongly Agree (Lubos na Sumasangayon)

It would be easy for me to become skillful at using the Virtual Memoriscapes Toolkit and the CALSADA AR. *

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree (Lubos na Di-Sumasangayon) Strongly Agree (Lubos na Sumasangayon)

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I would find the Virtual Memoriscapes Toolkit and the CALSADA AR easy to use *

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree (Lubos na Di-Sumasangayon) Strongly Agree (Lubos na Sumasangayon)

The information within the Virtual Memoriscapes Toolkit and the CALSADA AR was well organized, so I could easily find and know the information I needed. *

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree (Lubos na Di-Sumasangayon) Strongly Agree (Lubos na Sumasangayon)

The amount of time involved in using the Virtual Memoriscapes Toolkit and the CALSADA AR has been fitting for me. *

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree (Lubos na Di-Sumasangayon) Strongly Agree (Lubos na Sumasangayon)

Using the Virtual Memoriscapes Toolkit and the CALSADA AR did not require a lot of mental or creative effort. *

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree (Lubos na Di-Sumasangayon) Strongly Agree (Lubos na Sumasangayon)

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CONTENT QUALITY

I would find the amount of information about the history and narrative of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip in the Virtual Memoriscapes Toolkit and the CALSADA AR to be credible and accurate. *

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree (Lubos na Di-Sumasangayon) Strongly Agree (Lubos na Sumasangayon)

I would find the amount of localized information about streetscapes in the Virtual Memoriscapes Toolkit and the CALSADA AR to be fitting in what I see in my daily life. *

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree (Lubos na Di-Sumasangayon) Strongly Agree (Lubos na Sumasangayon)

I would find the amount of localized information about streetscapes in the Virtual Memoriscapes Toolkit and the CALSADA AR to be sufficient. *

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree (Lubos na Di-Sumasangayon) Strongly Agree (Lubos na Sumasangayon)

I would find the amount of localized information about history and narrative of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip in the Virtual Memoriscapes Toolkit and the CALSADA AR to be sufficient. *

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree (Lubos na Di-Sumasangayon) Strongly Agree (Lubos na Sumasangayon)

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SYSTEM QUALITY

I would find the presentation of the user interface of the Virtual Memoriscapes Toolkit and the CALSADA AR to be aesthetically pleasing and functional. *

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree (Lubos na Di-Sumasangayon) Strongly Agree (Lubos na Sumasangayon)

I would find the presentation of the physical cards within the Virtual Memoriscapes Toolkit and the CALSADA AR to be aesthetically pleasing and functional. *

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree (Lubos na Di-Sumasangayon) Strongly Agree (Lubos na Sumasangayon)

I would find the presentation of the 3D models within the Virtual Memoriscapes Toolkit and the CALSADA AR to be aesthetically pleasing and functional. *

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree (Lubos na Di-Sumasangayon) Strongly Agree (Lubos na Sumasangayon)

I would find the features (screenshot/reset button) within the main user interface * of the Virtual Memoriscapes Toolkit and the CALSADA AR to be aesthetically pleasing and functional.

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree (Lubos na Di-Sumasangayon) Strongly Agree (Lubos na Sumasangayon)

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INTERACTION QUALITY

I would find the augmented 3D models within the Virtual Memoriscapes Toolkit * and the CALSADA AR to be immersive and interactive.

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree (Lubos na Di-Sumasangayon) Strongly Agree (Lubos na Sumasangayon)

I would find the physical cards within the Virtual Memoriscapes Toolkit and the CALSADA AR to be immersive and interactive. *

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree (Lubos na Di-Sumasangayon) Strongly Agree (Lubos na Sumasangayon)

I would find the experience of seeing the 3D models being augmented in the physical cards in real time within the Virtual Memoriscapes Toolkit and the CALSADA AR to be highly interactive and immersive. *

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree (Lubos na Di-Sumasangayon) Strongly Agree (Lubos na Sumasangayon)

I would find the experience of pressing the buttons within the main user interface * of the Virtual Memoriscapes Toolkit and the CALSADA AR to be highly interactive and immersive.

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree (Lubos na Di-Sumasangayon) Strongly Agree (Lubos na Sumasangayon)

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VIRTUAL ATTACHMENT AND LIKELIHOOD OF USAGE

I intend to continue using the Virtual Memoriscapes toolkit and the CALSADA AR in the future. *

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree (Lubos na Di-Sumasangayon) Strongly Agree (Lubos na Sumasangayon)

I plan to continue using the Virtual Memoriscapes toolkit and the CALSADA AR frequently in the future. *

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree (Lubos na Di-Sumasangayon) Strongly Agree (Lubos na Sumasangayon)

I predict that I will use the Virtual Memoriscapes toolkit and the CALSADA AR on a regular basis in the future. *

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree (Lubos na Di-Sumasangayon) Strongly Agree (Lubos na Sumasangayon)

Assuming that I have access to the Virtual Memoriscapes Toolkit and the CALSADA AR, I would intend to use it. *

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree (Lubos na Di-Sumasangayon) Strongly Agree (Lubos na Sumasangayon)

I am able to care for the existing and lost heritage of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip after I have used the Virtual Memoriscapes Toolkit and the CALSADA AR. *

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree (Lubos na Di-Sumasangayon) Strongly Agree (Lubos na Sumasangayon)

I am able to understand the history and legacy of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip in Manila's Cinematic and Commercial History after I have used the Virtual Memoriscapes Toolkit and the CALSADA AR. *

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree (Lubos na Di-Sumasangayon) Strongly Agree (Lubos na Sumasangayon)

I am able to lobby for the revitalization of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip after I have used the Virtual Memoriscapes Toolkit and the CALSADA AR. *

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree (Lubos na Di-Sumasangayon) Strongly Agree (Lubos na Sumasangayon)

I am likely to forge meaningful relationships with my co-attendees and my fellow community members after I have used the Virtual Memoriscapes Toolkit and the CALSADA AR. *

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree (Lubos na Di-Sumasangayon) Strongly Agree (Lubos na Sumasangayon)

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Post-Workshop Questionnaire

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* Indicates required question

THANK YOU VERY MUCH!

Comments, feedbacks, or suggestions about the conduct of the workshop, or for * the improvement of the application

Your answer

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